

AGIMUS

INNOVATIVE ROBOTICS FOR AGILE PRODUCTION

PR2 Deliverables Ethics
Evaluation

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1. Introduction

In the previous project review meeting, a critical recommendation was made by the reviewers regarding the integration of ethical considerations within the AGIMUS project, in particular on adhering to the European Commission's Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI.

Recommendation #7 : Ethics and Trustworthy AI: Develop a detailed strategy for incorporating and operationalizing the EC's Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, ensuring ethical considerations are integrated into the development and deployment processes.

While the EC Ethics guidelines had been considered in the lead up to the project (D1.1), and reflected upon at the project level, the potential misuse of some of the scientific and technological advances of the project had not be considered until recently. To address ethical concerns more effectively in the context of the AGIMUS project, and better address the robotic field specificity within the ALTAI framework, we thus proposed (D1.3) the following strategy that integrates and builds upon existing efforts:

- **Consolidation of Insights**: we will consolidate recent insights and methodologies from other EU projects focused on robotics (e.g., Robotics4EU, euROBIN) on ethics. This will help harmonize our approach with the best practices already developed and ensure consistency across initiatives.
- **Enhancement of Ethics Tools**: we will enhance the existing AGIMUS AI ethics checklist of the project, which currently incorporates elements from the ALTAI, by explicitly integrating considerations specific to robotics (i.e., hardware impact and considerations). This augmented checklist will serve as a critical tool for assessing the ethical dimensions of the innovations stemming from AGIMUS.
- **Robust Evaluation Process**: we will implement a robust review process where all new deliverables due for the second review are rigorously evaluated through this enhanced ethical checklist. This process ensures that every aspect of our project not only meets technical standards but also aligns with ethical guidelines, thereby promoting responsible innovation and fostering trust in our robotics applications.

This context underpins our ongoing ethics discussions and provides a structured pathway for embedding ethical integrity throughout the AGIMUS project life-cycle.

2. Reflecting on the ethics review process

In the Ethics Workshop (3 x 1h-sessions that occurred on April 29th and 30th and on May 6th), we focused on aligning our initial assessment of the EC Ethics guidelines with a proposed methodology for assessing individual deliverable. This effort is crucial for ensuring that our ethical considerations are consistent and adequately addressed at both the project-wide and deliverable-specific levels.

The discussion encompass the identification of ethical risks, the application of various assessment tools, and specific challenges and recommendations for moving forward.

Evaluation of Ethical Risks in Project Outcomes

Attention was directed toward evaluating the ethical risks associated with the project's outcomes. - The project team conducted a self-review for this reporting period, despite not being experts in ethics. - Leveraging their expertise in robotics, the team aims to provide a sufficiently robust ethical assessment at this stage. - There is a possibility that this evaluation may require supplementation. In instances where project results may pose substantial ethical risks, the team is prepared to undertake more detailed and comprehensive analysis to thoroughly address the specific ethical concerns identified. - Should our internal evaluation prove insufficient from the reviewers' perspective, we are ready to formally seek feedback from the Ethics Advisory Board (EAB). This may involve establishing a new EAB or consulting with an external ethics expert, particularly if specific ethical issues arise.

Evaluation Frameworks and Tools

In our ongoing efforts to effectively integrate ethical considerations into the AGIMUS project and align with the European Commission's (EC) guidelines on Trustworthy AI, a thorough evaluation of existing methods and tools was conducted. Below are the key insights and conclusions drawn from these discussions:

- Expected-Value Procedure (EVP) & Precautionary Principle (PP) evaluation methods: These methods focus on balancing probabilities against uncertainties, offering a structured way to assess potential risks. However, implementing these methods requires developing a comprehensive evaluation framework, which is currently beyond the scope of our current project resources.
- Exploration of Existing Tools:
 - Developed under the Robotics4EU initiative, RoboCompass (<https://robocompass.aiod.eu>) offers a detailed self-evaluation process where risks and mitigation strategies are scored across various domains. It has been determined that applying RoboCompass at the individual deliverable level within AGIMUS is impractical. The tool is too cumbersome for fine-grained application due to questions that are primarily relevant for robotic product deployment at TRL levels much higher than AGIMUS. Furthermore, existing technical issues with the online tool (errors when generating the final report) hinder its usability in the current form.
 - RRI-Tools (<https://caixaresearch.org/en/caixaresearch-rri-tools>) has also been identified but no actual implementation is available at the time of evaluation.

Human Oversight and Agency in Robotics

The discussion focused on the essential aspects of human oversight and agency in advanced robotics. - It was emphasized that human empowerment and the ability to ensure safety, such as being able to intervene or stop robotic processes when necessary, are fundamental to human oversight. - Human oversight is not directly addressed within the scientific work packages WP2/WP3/WP4 as they focus on low-level control of robots (e.g., contact detection and trajectory optimization). - The complexity of many lower-level automated decisions necessitates explainability. While basic operators cannot be expected to understand complex mathematical processes, the project aims to facilitate a clear understanding of these processes. - The need exists to implement oversight mechanisms at higher levels, particularly by robot manufacturers, to fortify a “safety by design” approach. - Moreover, it was advised to revisit and comment on discussions regarding oversight and agency documented in D1.1, ensuring these considerations are thoroughly reflected in project documentation.

Robot Safety and Human Interaction

The participants also discussed the implications of deploying safer robotic technologies in industrial settings. Currently, industrial robots tend to operate in safe zone without human operators due to their inherent dangers. The AGIMUS project aspires to enhance robot safety, potentially enabling closer interactions between robots and humans.

These advances are expected to promote the deployment of robots in proximity to humans, which raise concerns about increased risks of accidents. As a precautionary measure, it was suggested that a disclaimer might be necessary to acknowledge and address these potential risks, thus ensuring transparency and preparedness in mitigating such outcomes.

3. Deliverables Ethical Review

Overall, while some elements such as fundamental rights and human agency were deemed not relevant due to the project focus and early stage, key aspects like human oversight, technical safety, and privacy were adjusted to Agimus unique context while maintaining compliance with the underlying values of the EC ethics guidelines. The self-assessment checklist was thus adapted to account for these changes. During the workshop, we evaluated each deliverable according to this updated checklist:

- **Safety:** The assessment indicates the level and nature of safety impacts, explaining if the deliverable introduces risks or enhancements.
- **Privacy:** Determines the applicability and impact on privacy, indicating whether it’s relevant or not.
- **Transparency:** Discusses how openness affects the project, with explanations about open-source status or lack thereof.
- **Societal and Environmental Well-being:** Describes the broader impacts, including potential societal benefits or risks.

- **Accountability:** Summarizes how responsibility and decision-making transparency are handled, detailing positive or limited contributions.

D1.3 AGIMUS System Requirements and Architecture - Second Version

- **Deadline:** Month 24
- **Lead Partner:** TOWARD
- **Type:** Architecture and Methodology
- **Evaluation Summary:**
 - The deliverable D1.3 presents two contributions: the updated AGIMUS architecture and an operational methodology to address ethics guidelines within the AGIMUS project. As the updated architecture does not raise any new ethical considerations, and the methodology is structured such that ethical concerns are predominantly addressed in the other deliverables, this specific deliverable is free from direct ethical issues.
 - Safety: Not applicable
 - Privacy: Not applicable
 - Transparency: Not applicable
 - Societal and Environmental Well-being: Not applicable
 - Accountability: Not applicable

D2.2 Efficient and Versatile Differentiable Simulator

- **Deadline:** Month 24
- **Lead Partner:** INRIA
- **Type:** Scientific Findings
- **Evaluation Summary:**
 - **Safety:** Although it is fundamentally a scientific tool, its broader implications are neutral in terms of immediate safety risks.
 - **Privacy:** Privacy considerations are not applicable to this deliverable, as it primarily involves software development rather than handling personal data.
 - **Transparency:** Transparency is a concern, as the DiffCoal component of the differentiable simulator, is not currently open-source. The lack of source code delivery affects dependencies and may hinder other software that relies on it.
 - **Societal and Environmental Well-being:** The simulator serves as a fundamental brick with dual-use potential, making it applicable to a wide range of robotic applications. Notably, INRIA has reported contacts from companies involved in military drone development with interests for DiffCoal, highlighting the dual-use concern.
 - **Accountability:** There are no specific accountability issues related to this deliverable, as its primary function is as a research and development tool.

D2.4 Trajectory Optimizer with Constraints and Task-and-Motion Planner

- **Deadline:** Month 30
- **Lead Partner:** INRIA
- **Type:** Scientific Findings
- **Evaluation Summary:**
 - **Safety:** The trajectory optimizer contributes significantly to the project’s “safety by design” objectives by enhancing safety through hard constraints. However, there are potential side effects if the technology is used prematurely in environments where current robots are not deemed safe, raising concerns about readiness and operational safety. While this deliverable presents more advanced capabilities, it is still less robust than existing solutions.
 - **Privacy:** Privacy issues are not applicable to this deliverable given its focus on optimizing robotic trajectories without involving personal data.
 - **Transparency:** There is a high degree of transparency, as the Aligator software associated with this deliverable is open-source, allowing for broad access and review.
 - **Societal and Environmental Well-being:** There is currently low risk on dual-use usage and no specific companies have expressed interest. Energy efficiency has not been a focus yet of the evaluation and benchmarking in trajectory optimization, especially when comparing with solutions based on small neural networks deployed on small platforms, counterbalancing trends towards larger models. This deliverable contributes to increased automation, promising productivity and reduced operator burden but potentially impacting job availability and quality.
 - **Accountability:** The optimizer’s decision-making process delegates to algorithms with strong mathematical foundations, offering high levels of explainability. Although formal proof of all cases is pending, traceability and accountability are improved, marking progress towards full explainability.

D3.2 Planner Guided by Demonstration Extracted from a Monocular Camera - Final Version

- **Deadline:** Month 27
- **Lead Partner:** CTU
- **Type:** Scientific Findings
- **Evaluation Summary:**
 - This deliverable focuses on developing a planner guided by demonstrations captured through a monocular camera. The key aim is to enhance reasoning capabilities without directly controlling the robot, with safety aspects managed at lower operational levels. Although this approach may seem to contradict the project’s safety goals, it mainly targets high-level safety.
 - **Safety:** Not directly applicable here as the safety is managed at lower levels. This deliverable focuses on reasoning, not controlling the robot.

- **Privacy:** Utilizes human data from professional operators in a controlled environment. Legal issues are addressed through contracts, although the risk of losing expertise is noted as a societal impact.
- **Transparency:** The deliverable is transparent, with code provided and no storage of video data. The process by which video is used is clear.
- **Societal and Environmental Well-being:** There are concerns about the potential loss of human expertise, which is a general consequence of automation.
- **Accountability:** The system enhances planning and decision-making, enabling non-experts to program the robot. It facilitates decision-making processes that can be explained, thus supporting accountability.

D3.3 Motion Dataset from the Planner Created through Supervised Learning

- **Deadline:** Month 24
- **Lead Partner:** CNRS
- **Type:** Scientific Findings
- **Evaluation Summary:**
 - This deliverable contributes a motion dataset developed through supervised learning, categorized under scientific findings. Unlike other datasets, it does not involve human video data, aligning with privacy requirements.
 - **Safety:** The design incorporates safety principles, integrating a motion planner, machine learning, and controllers with inherent safety measures inherited from earlier deliverables such as D2.4.
 - **Privacy:** Not an issue here, as the dataset uses automatically generated data rather than human data.
 - **Transparency:** Although the neural network decision-making is not directly explainable or transparent, all materials are open source, allowing experts to recreate the neural network.
 - **Societal and Environmental Well-being:** The deliverable minimizes environmental impact by limiting the size of neural networks, indicating a shift toward cost-saving cloud services.
 - **Accountability:** Compared to direct neural network control methods, this deliverable improves accountability by integrating a mathematical solver, thus building upon previous methods.

D4.2 6D Object Pose Estimation with a Partial View and Physical Priors

- **Deadline:** Month 24
- **Lead Partner:** CTU
- **Type:** Scientific Findings
- **Evaluation Summary:**

- This deliverable offers scientific advancements in 6D object pose estimation utilizing partial views and physical priors. While technical robustness is enhanced compared to previous methodologies, its safety implications largely depend on downstream applications, such as those in D4.4.
- **Safety:** The deliverable enhances technical robustness, but its safety improvements are contingent upon its application. Thus, this component in itself is not directly applicable to safety considerations.
- **Privacy:** Potentially applicable for user activity monitoring, though no human data is involved during training, nor is it stored during runtime, mitigating substantial privacy concerns.
- **Transparency:** The algorithm is open-source, with transparent operations that are largely self-explanatory due to explicit algorithmic steps. However, diagnosing malfunctions may require third-party intervention.
- **Societal and Environmental Well-being:** The training demands significant computational resources, which could impact environmental sustainability, while runtime requires large GPU cards, highlighting potential resource concerns.
- **Accountability:** While accountability is somewhat off-topic for this deliverable, component failures are not self-diagnosable, necessitating third-party oversight. Data/code/training versioning is effectively monitored, enhancing traceability.

D4.4 Sensor-driven MPC with Visual-Haptic Feedback - First Version

- **Deadline:** Month 27
- **Lead Partner:** CNRS
- **Type:** Scientific Findings
- **Evaluation Summary:**
 - As this deliverable is yet to be submitted, a detailed evaluation remains pending.
 - **Safety:** Evaluation not available at this stage.
 - **Privacy:** Evaluation not available at this stage.
 - **Transparency:** Evaluation not available at this stage.
 - **Societal and Environmental Well-being:** Evaluation not available at this stage.
 - **Accountability:** Evaluation not available at this stage.

D5.2 Preparation, integration, and testing at AGIMUS testing zones

- **Deadline:** Month 27
- **Lead Partner:** PAL
- **Type:** Technological Development
- **Evaluation Summary:**
 - As this deliverable is yet to be submitted, a detailed evaluation remains pending.

- **Safety:** Evaluation not available at this stage.
- **Privacy:** Evaluation not available at this stage.
- **Transparency:** Evaluation not available at this stage.
- **Societal and Environmental Well-being:** Evaluation not available at this stage.
- **Accountability:** Evaluation not available at this stage.

D6.1 Specification of the industrial pilot case studies

- **Deadline:** Month 18
- **Lead Partner:** KLEEMANN
- **Type:** Industrial Deployment
- **Evaluation Summary:**
 - **Safety:** Safety of the integration of the AGIMUS’s robotic solution is addressed in the architecture of the platform, while the safety of each industrial deployment is handled by each partner.
 - **Privacy:** Not explicitly addressed, as this report primarily centers on industrial processes and robotic integration.
 - **Transparency:** The document contributes to transparency by offering a detailed specification of industrial case studies and the methodologies used to assess and mitigate risks.
 - **Societal and Environmental Well-being:** Not relevant.
 - **Accountability:** Accountability is reinforced through structured case study definitions, regular meetings, and collaborative discussions among partners.

D6.4 Cross Pilot Technical and Non-Technical Comparative Assessment

- **Deadline:** Month 18
- **Lead Partner:** AIRBUS
- **Type:** Industrial Deployment
- **Evaluation Summary:**
 - This preliminary report outlines general directions for the evaluation of industrial pilots within the AGIMUS project. Building on previous deliverables, the report indirectly addresses ethical issues already explored in other project documents. It emphasizes the importance of not only defining technical criteria for assessment but also incorporating non-technical aspects, such as ethics and trustworthiness, to ensure a holistic evaluation approach.
 - **Safety:** Safety is indirectly handled through the AGIMUS architecture (WP1).
 - **Privacy:** Not relevant at this stage.
 - **Privacy:** While the industrial pilots are not processing personal data, specific privacy arising from the on-site deployment of each case study is handled by the responsible partner.

- **Transparency:** The use of clear metrics and open dissemination of best practices and policy recommendations enhances stakeholder understanding and trust.
- **Societal and Environmental Well-being:**
- **Accountability:**

D7.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activities

- **Deadline:** Month 24
- **Lead Partner:** Q-PLAN
- **Type:** Organizational and Strategic
- **Evaluation Summary:**
 - **Safety:** The deliverable focuses on dissemination and communication strategies, thus safety is not relevant here.
 - **Privacy:** Privacy concerns are indirectly addressed through the management of collected data, such as website analytics and social media interactions (compliance with GDPR).
 - **Transparency:** Addressed by detailing the communication strategy, dissemination activities, and partners' responsibilities.
 - **Societal and Environmental Well-being:** Addressed thru the inclusion of criteria such as trustworthiness, energy consumption, ensuring that the deployment of technologies respects human rights and promotes societal well-being.
 - **Accountability:** The deliverable establishes an accountable framework for assessing the pilots.

D7.5 Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

- **Deadline:** Month 24
- **Lead Partner:** Q-PLAN
- **Type:** Organizational and Strategic
- **Evaluation Summary:**
 - The deliverable addresses ethical considerations by promoting transparent and accountable IP management strategies, which ensure partners have clear roles and access rights. By providing a robust framework for managing innovation, the plan ensures ethical handling of the project's key results and continued alignment with project goals and ethical standards.
 - **Safety:** Addresses IP management and business planning, not directly physical or operational safety issues. Ensuring robust IP management indirectly supports safety by regulating how technology is deployed and maintained.
 - **Privacy:** Not explicitly considered
 - **Transparency:** Emphasizes transparency by detailing IP management strategies, methodologies, and key concepts, fostering better awareness among consortium partners.

- **Societal and Environmental Well-being:** Promotes responsible and sustainable post-project exploitation practices.
- **Accountability:** Outlines roles and methodologies that establish clear lines of responsibility for managing exploitation

D8.3 Data Management Plan

- **Deadline:** Month 24
- **Lead Partner:** Q-PLAN
- **Type:** Organizational and Strategic
- **Evaluation Summary:**
 - Ethical issues related to AGIMUS's DMP have been addressed in the deliverable, highlighting its compliance with GDPR. The DMP includes compliant privacy policies and consent forms, and ensures no personal data will be transferred outside the EU. Each project partner is responsible for adapting these documents to their specific legal contexts and maintaining records of consent, ensuring ethical data handling throughout the project.
 - **Safety:** Safety handled at the platform level.
 - **Privacy:** Safeguarded by adhering to GDPR guidelines
 - **Transparency:** Achieved by adhering to GDPR principles, ensuring that data processing is conducted lawfully and transparently, and by providing open access to policies and forms.
 - **Societal and Environmental Well-being:** Primarily focuses on data management and protection, thus it does not directly address these aspects.
 - **Accountability:** Ensured by mandating each partner to tailor privacy documentation to their specific legal contexts, maintain records of consent, and implement mechanisms to withdraw consent.

4. Conclusion

In reflecting on the integration of ethical considerations within the AGIMUS project, it has become apparent that a comprehensive ethical study plan from the outset would have been beneficial. While the project is not a traditional research endeavor but focused more on industrial deployment, emphasizing agile production and robotics, the ethical implications are significant. Initial groundwork laid in Deliverable D1.3 needs to be revisited in D1.4, while the exploitation aspects in D7.6 should work towards finalizing the project's ethical framework, particularly given the potential dual-use nature of the technologies developed. This approach ensures that ethical considerations are systematically integrated into the project's lifecycle, aligning with its strategic industrial goals.

Summary Table

Deliverable	Deadline	Lead Partner	Safety	Privacy	Transparency	Societal and Environmental Well-being	Accountability
D2.2 Efficient and Versatile Differentiable Simulator	M24	INRIA	Limited Negative - Scientific tool, fundamental, dual-use risk	Not Applicable	Medium Negative - Not open-source, impacts dependencies	Medium Negative - Dual-use potential, military contact	Not Applicable
D2.4 Trajectory Optimizer with Constraints and Task-and-Motion Planner	M30	INRIA	Medium Positive - Enhances safety, premature tech risk	Not Applicable	Positive - Open-source	Medium Mixed - Automation benefits and job impact concerns	Limited Positive - Mathematically grounded, explainable
D1.3 AGIMUS System Requirements and Architecture - Second Version	M24	TOWARD	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Not Applicable
D3.2 Planner Guided by Demonstration Extracted from a Monocular Camera - Final Version	M27	CTU	Limited, managed at lower levels	Limited - Professional use, contracts in place	High - Code provided, process clear	Limited - Potential loss of expertise	Medium Positive - Enhances decision-making, explainable
D3.3 Motion Dataset from the Planner Created through Supervised Learning	M24	CNRS	Medium - Inherited safety	Not Applicable	Medium - Open source, expert use	Medium Positive - Low environmental impact, cost-saving	Medium Positive - Integrates solver, builds on previous methods
D4.2 6D Object Pose Estimation with a Partial View and Physical Priors	M24	CTU	Limited Positive - Depends on use	Limited - No human data storage	Medium - Open source, but needs third-party for diagnostics	Negative - High computational cost	Limited - Needs third-party for accountability

Summary Table

Deliverable	Deadline	Lead Partner	Safety	Privacy	Transparency	Societal and Environmental Well-being	Accountability
D4.4 Sensor-driven MPC with Visual-Haptic Feedback - First Version	M27	CNRS	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
D5.2 Preparation, Integration, and Testing at AGIMUS Testing Zones	M27	PAL	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Not Applicable
D6.1 Specification of the Industrial Pilot Case Studies	M18	KLEEM ANN	Limited Impact - Architecture Level	Not Applicable	Medium Positive - Clear Methodologies	Not Applicable	Medium Positive - Structured Discussions
D6.4 Cross Pilot Technical and Non-Technical Comparative Assessment	M18	AIRBUS	Indirect	Limited On-site handled by partners	Medium Metrics and Best Practices	Medium Positive Ethical Considerations	Medium Positive Framework and Recommendations
D7.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activities	M24	Q-PLAN	Not Applicable	Limited Data Management	Medium Positive Strategy and Responsibilities	Medium Positive Trustworthiness	Medium Positive - Clear Roles
D7.5 Exploitation and Sustainability Plan	M24	Q-PLAN	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Strong Positive - IP Management Strategy	Medium Positive Responsible Practices	Medium Positive - Clear Guidelines
D8.3 Data Management Plan	M24	Q-PLAN	Limited Impact - Platform Level	Strong Positive - GDPR Compliance	Strong Positive - GDPR Principles	Not Applicable	Strong Positive - Tailored Documentation